

ECONOMIC RELATIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN WITH THE COUNTRIES OF THE ORGANIZATION OF ISLAMIC COOPERATION (END OF 20TH CENTURY - BEGINNING OF 21ST CENTURY)

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Abstract

Among the important conditions of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation are the development and strengthening of multilateral relations between Muslim states, the establishment of financial and economic cooperation between these countries, and the establishment of new, higher-quality international economic rules for Islamic countries.

Azerbaijan, being an active member of the organization, is making efforts to expand economic and financial ties with other countries and to increase trade. In this sense, the natural gas exchange agreement signed between Azerbaijan, Iran, and Turkmenistan in November 2021 can be seen as a new dynamic in the Caucasus-Caspian region. When studying economic relations with OIC member countries, the doubling of natural gas transportation between three OIC members - Azerbaijan, Iran and Turkmenistan, as well as the establishment of new communication links between Azerbaijan and Iran are important stages in the development of economic relations between these countries. Azerbaijan's positive economic partnerships with its close neighbors and Central Asian countries are strengthening within the OIC, both bilaterally and multilaterally. Azerbaijan is one of the five countries in the Caspian Sea, including Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan, and acts on the international stage as an active member of the Organization of Turkic States, as well as other international organizations covering the Central Asian region. In its activities within the OIC, the Republic of Azerbaijan also puts forward its proposals for solving important problems, including financial issues, and does not spare financial support when necessary.

The article examines economic issues with Azerbaijan's close regional neighbors, the Muslim CIS countries, and various OIC member countries.

Keywords: OIC countries, economic relations, financial issues, Islamic banking, Azerbaijani economy.

Economic integration processes originating in Western Europe are rapidly expanding and encompassing virtually all regions of the modern world, including North Africa and the Middle East. The changing geopolitical situation has created opportunities for the economic world to become multipolar. At present, only a part of global trade can be described as 'classical, the rest is non-classical, falling under the influence of the strategy of active associations of various powers uniting in alliances, transnational corporations and financial-industrial groups. In this regard, the rapprochement of Islamic countries, in turn, has its own unique characteristics and creates a need for research in these areas.

Since its inception, the Organization of Islamic Cooperation has prioritized economic cooperation among its member states. Thus, at the Organization's first conference, held in Jeddah in March 1970, the neocolonial policies of Western countries were discussed, and the idea of creating a special economic union for the purpose of economic cooperation among Muslims of the world was voiced. An important indicator of economic cooperation can be considered the second conference (Lahore) within the OIC, at which the Lahore Declaration was adopted, and a special committee on economic cooperation of OIC countries was created, which included representatives from Algeria, Egypt, Kuwait, BRI, Pakistan, Senegal, Libya and Saudi Arabia [9; 10].

The experience of the Cooperation Council for the Arab States of the Gulf (GCC), established in May 1981, has shown that a relatively promising mechanism for economic integration in the Muslim world is the unification of countries with approximately the same

economic level, similar in governance methods, political regimes, cultural indicators and at the same time located in close geographical areas. Despite the existence of some territorial problems between the countries that are part of this union, they can take a unified position in solving several international problems, supporting productive political and economic cooperation [9, p.385]. OIC countries consider the creation of a common economic space and the organization of a "single space" of stock exchanges as important areas in the field of economic cooperation. The preparation of framework agreements related to economic privileges for OIC member countries is regularly included on the agenda. In this regard, at the OIC session held in Istanbul in 2005, a protocol on the gradual elimination of customs, tariff and other economic barriers within the OIC was presented. In other words, Islamic countries do not deny their desire to create a single economic and political space in the future. As one of the methods of economic solidarity, proposals are also being put forward to define a denomination that would play the role of a special currency in trade transactions between Muslim countries. For example, former Malaysian Prime Minister Mahathir Mohamad has repeatedly put forward the idea of using an "Islamic gold dinar" [12, pp. 1-3].

Main directions of economic relations between Azerbaijan and OIC countries

It would be correct to link the establishment of a few successful political and economic cooperation with Muslim countries within the OIC with the correct political course of the Great Leader. At the summit held in Islamabad in March 1995, Azerbaijan also participated

in the signing of agreements on transit trade and simplified visa issuance for businessmen from the countries of the Economic Cooperation Organization and development, the creation and charter of shipbuilding companies of the OIC countries, the creation and charter of airlines of the OIC countries. In November of the same year, an agreement was signed between the Arab Republic of Egypt and the Republic of Azerbaijan on the export of oil refining equipment from Azerbaijan to Egypt [2, p. 1061].

When considering issues of economic cooperation between Azerbaijan and OIC member countries, the first thing that comes to mind are the Muslim countries that are close in territory. Among them, the most relevant from the point of view of close proximity is the study of trade and economic relations with Iran. It can be said that the above-mentioned relations between the two countries developed unstable during the period from 1990 to 2022 against the backdrop of changes in political relations. Thus, if in 1995 the share of the Islamic Republic of Iran in the total trade turnover with the Republic of Azerbaijan was 20.4%, then in 2000-2021 this figure decreased significantly (2.2-1.30%) and finally reached its lowest point in 2022 (0.96%) [4, p.105]. Economists explain the sharp decline in the share of the Islamic Republic of Iran in trade turnover with Azerbaijan, on the one hand, by the diversification of the country's economy, and on the other hand, by the implementation of various projects, especially energy ones, which resulted in a significant increase in the number of economic partners. It is gratifying that during 2000-2007, exports from Azerbaijan to Iran increased 57 times compared to previous years, reaching 437.7 million US dollars. The higher level of imports in 2022 was 476.4 million US dollars. The sharp decline and rise in economic indicators between the two countries is explained not only by the economic factors, but also by the level of relations in the political sphere, as well as the period of the COVID-19 pandemic. It can be noted that among more than 1000 types of products exported from Iran to Azerbaijan, the top three places are occupied by polyethylene products, unprocessed aluminum and butter. Significant differences are also observed in the import of certain food products into Azerbaijan. For example, oil imports increased 14-fold over the course of one year (2021-2022), while potato imports decreased fourfold [4, p. 106].

The natural gas exchange agreement signed between Azerbaijan, Iran, and Turkmenistan in November 2021 can be considered a new dynamic in the Caucasus-Caspian region. According to the document, it was planned to supply 1.5-2 billion cubic meters of gas per year. In June 2022, the parties decided to double gas transportation between the three OIC member countries. Iran is interested in taking an important place in the railway and road transport system connecting Asia and Europe through the South Caucasus. In this regard, in March 2022, Azerbaijan and Iran signed a memorandum on the establishment of new communications links. The memorandum envisages the creation of a transport network linking Iran with Azerbaijan's East Zangezur region, as well as with the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, and power supply lines. According

to the document, the new corridor will include the construction of four bridges and two railway lines across the Araz River, as well as the development of communications and energy infrastructure, which will open up favorable opportunities for Iran to serve as a transit corridor between Azerbaijan and Turkey. Thanks to this corridor, Azerbaijan will be able to establish a short land connection with Nakhchivan [4, p. 110]. The commissioning of the Khudaferin and Giz Galasi hydroelectric power plants in May 2024 will undoubtedly have a positive impact on significantly strengthening Azerbaijani Iranian relations in the energy sector. In his speech at the commissioning ceremony of the Khudaferin Hydroelectric Power Station and the opening of the Giz Galasi Hydroelectric Power Station, President Ilham Aliyev praised the efforts of Azerbaijan and Iran to create the North-South Transport Corridor, noting the special role of transport projects and that the North-South transport corridor will become one of the most important transport routes in the world, and noted that freight traffic along this route has already increased by more than 50% in a short period of time [1]. It's worth noting that Azerbaijan, one of the five countries that also includes two Caspian Basin countries—Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan—has chaired the Non-Aligned Movement since 2019 is an active member of the Organization of Turkic States, as well as other international organizations covering the Central Asian region. The country, which has begun to establish close political and economic relations with its neighbors, located to the west of the Caspian Sea, was able to implement large trans-Caspian projects back in the 1990s. Among these, we would like to highlight the growth of trade with Central Asian countries using the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway, the transportation of Kazakh oil via the Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan pipeline, and the joint exploitation of the Dostlug offshore field with Turkmenistan. Along with all this, the Zangezur Corridor project should also be mentioned. Its implementation will thus create opportunities for Azerbaijan and Armenia to establish direct transport links with Turkey and the countries of Central Asia. As a result of close relations with the Central Asian countries, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev in his speech, particularly emphasized that in 2022, trade with Central Asian countries increased by 50% over 7 months, and over the next three years, it is planned to increase mutual investments by more than US\$1 billion. It should be noted that several projects are currently being implemented in the areas of industrial cooperation, mechanical engineering, automotive industry, shipbuilding, agriculture (especially cotton growing, sericulture, horticulture and animal husbandry), and the interest of companies from Central Asian countries in the Alat Economic Zone is growing [15].

Economic cooperation is one of the essential areas of relations between Tajikistan and Azerbaijan. The Intergovernmental Commission on Trade and Economic Cooperation, established in 2011, serves as an important coordinating mechanism for economic relations between these countries. The main areas of economic cooperation between Azerbaijan and Tajikistan are joint projects in the field of non-ferrous metallurgy, development of the agro-industrial complex, energy, light

industry, transport, communications, mining industry, and the financial sector [13]. In September 1996, in Baku, by decision of the Islamic Development Bank and its affiliated structures, an International Investment Conference was held, which marked the beginning of a new stage in resolving economic and financial issues between Azerbaijan and the OIC. The event, which was attended by the bank's president, official and accredited members of the Board of Directors, was attended by up to 200 participants from 17 countries. In 1997, the Board of Directors of the Islamic Development Bank allocated a preferential loan to Azerbaijan in the amount of 13.151 million US dollars, which was intended for the reconstruction of roads on the Alat-Hajigabul line. Overall, the Islamic Development Bank has regularly provided financial assistance to Azerbaijan, providing more than US\$70 billion in concessional loans and even US\$5 billion in grants. Given the dire economic situation in Azerbaijan following the First Karabakh War, it can be noted that a significant portion of financial assistance was directed towards the needs of internally displaced persons and humanitarian aid. In addition, the said financial resources were directed towards the construction of schools, various production facilities, road construction, creation of water supply networks, resolution of technical equipment issues, and implementation of socio-economically important projects [3, p.262]. Currently, the IDB has invested in 18 projects in the Azerbaijani economy alone, amounting to US\$1 billion [11].

Among the documents adopted following the 33rd session of the OIC, held in the capital of Azerbaijan, Baku, in 2006, was the final financial document of the Summit. The meeting adopted a resolution on the provision of assistance to Azerbaijan by OIC member states. This financial assistance was directed toward resolving the then-unresolved Karabakh conflict aiding internally displaced people [8].

In its activities within the OIC, the Republic of Azerbaijan also puts forward its proposals for solving important problems, including financial issues, and does not hesitate to provide financial support if necessary. At a briefing held on June 23, 2008, the press secretary of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Azerbaijan, Khazar Ibrahim, announced assistance in the amount of 500 thousand US dollars to change the international structure of the OIC [7, pp. 113-116]. We can link the country's commitment to financial support to its successful economic doctrine. Thus, between 2003 and 2008, the country's gross domestic product increased almost threefold [16, pp. 48-49]. Azerbaijan immediately responded to the request of member states of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation for assistance in connection with the tense socio-economic situation in the Sahel region of Africa. On the instructions of the country's President Ilham Aliyev, the Cabinet of Ministers allocated 100 thousand US dollars for these purposes [5]. In November 2024, an agreement was signed between President Ilham Aliyev and President of the Islamic Development Bank Mohammed Al Jasser on the construction of a main irrigation canal, which will start from the Maiden Fortress reservoir (in the territory of the Jebail region) [15].

Islamic banking, which has gained popularity in the financial world in recent years, has also begun to gain increasing relevance in the Eurasian region. The interest can be explained by the flow of investments into these regions, especially in Russia, the Caucasus, Central Asia, and the Middle East. Furthermore, the Islamic Development Bank, the largest bank in the Islamic world with a multi-million-dollar portfolio, frequently invests in various projects in the region. Attempts to introduce various forms of Islamic banking in Azerbaijan have been observed since the late 1990s, and this trend intensified between 2015 and 2021. In 2017, the Islamic Bank allocated a \$200,000 grant for the development of Islamic banking in Azerbaijan. The project's implementing agency is the Agency for the Development of Small and Medium-Sized Businesses under the Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Azerbaijan. To date, some work has been done in this area, with the IFAAS and EKVITA consortiums involved. It should be noted that two options for introducing Islamic banking in Azerbaijan are currently emerging. To achieve this, a new bill must be prepared, or the necessary changes must be made to the current legislation to create opportunities for the introduction of the main products of Islamic banking. This can be achieved by opening Islamic banking windows in existing banks. Clearly, Islamic banking is necessary for the implementation of alternative financial mechanisms in Azerbaijan [6]. At present, it can be said that the IDB has invested in the economy of Azerbaijan in only 18 projects, which amounts to 1 billion US dollars [11].

The OIC doctrine follows directly from the stated goals, which include such important provisions as the development and strengthening of various relations between Muslim states, financial and economic cooperation between the countries in question, establishing new international economic rules in which Islamic countries can have equal rights.

As a result of the efforts of the leadership of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the country has established close bilateral relations with many Muslim countries based on mutual understanding and trust, creating the foundations for stable, multifaceted relations. Furthermore, it should be considered that existing relations should gradually expand, mutual visits should be organized at various levels, and practical measures should be taken to implement joint projects in trade, economic, industrial, agricultural, investment, transit, transport and many other areas.

The agreement on the application of Islamic banking raises the issue of analyzing all existing opportunities for its application in Azerbaijan, considering the basic norms of Islamic banking. There is no doubt that legally regulated Islamic finance will open up new opportunities for banks and companies operating in the republic and will attract Islamic investors to Azerbaijan.

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